

UDC 027.7:004.77

SOBOLEVSKAYA Yu. V.

Scientific Library of the Belarusian National Technical University

(Republic of Belarus, Minsk), e-mail: sobol.yuli@gmail.com

WORK IN GROUP OR PERSONAL MAINTENANCE OF CORPORATE SOCIAL MEDIA

Objective. Social media have become one of the main technologies for promoting the university library. The purpose of the work is to characterize the main stages of organizing work in social media for librarians (SMM specialists and a working group) of the Scientific Library of the Belarusian National Technical University (BNTU). **Methods.** Statistical analysis tools made it possible to study in detail the corporate networks of the BNTU Library. A comparative analysis of the experience of maintaining BNTU accounts in social media by an SMM specialist and a working group of employees from various library departments was carried out. **Results.** The advantages and risks in the work of the group are summarized. The following areas highlighted: Team building; Communication and work organization; Creativity and creative power; Overcoming the challenges of group work; Content formation techniques; Potential. **Conclusions.** Working in a group produces creative and interesting content in large volumes. The experience of managing the process of forming a content policy in 2020 proves that the process has become more flexible and independent of the personality of an SMM specialist.

Keywords: social media; corporate networks of the university library; SMM specialist and working groups

Introduction

Working with information consumers is at the center of every library's activity. To expand the audience of users, library specialists strive to find effective means, forms and methods (Minasyan, 2019, Yap, 2020). Social media have become one of the main technologies for promoting the library. Representation in various social media is an effective channel for broadcasting information, a platform for various flash mobs and marathons, a source of direct communication and a messenger (Nechushkina, 2020).

The corporate networks of the Scientific Library of the Belarusian National Technical University (BNTU) originate from 2009, when accounts on Facebook, Twitter, VK were created, and later the list of our presence expanded.

Statistical analysis tools make it possible to study the audience in detail and choose an effective tactics for promoting library services. The result depends on the ability to correctly analyze and communicate with various groups of subscribers. University libraries are aimed at the student audience, accompany the educational and scientific process. It is important to choose an acceptable communication style and speak the same language.

The administration of our profiles and the content preparation was carried out by a specialist who led only the SMM direction. This approach is the most common. The character and personal style of an SSM specialist significantly affects the results of promotion on social networks. In connection with personnel changes in our library, this direction was led by various employees.

In 2020, work with the profiles of the BNTU Scientific Library in social media was organized in a fundamentally new format. A group of representatives from various departments was organized, who took the content preparation depending on the specifics of their work or interests.

The purpose of the work is to characterize the main stages in organizing work in social media for librarians (SMM specialists and a working group) of the Scientific Library of the Belarusian National Technical University (BNTU).

Methods

Using statistical analysis tools, the work of the corporate networks of the BNTU library was studied in detail: Facebook (<https://www.facebook.com/bntulibrary>), Twitter (<https://twitter.com/biblioteka>), VK (<https://vk.com/bntulibrary>), Instagram (<https://www.instagram.com/bntulibrary/>), Telegram (<https://t.me/scomlab>), Youtube (<https://www.youtube.com/user/BNTUlibrary>).

Then the author of the article, based on the data obtained and personal work experience in the group, carried out a comparative analysis of the main organizational factors affecting the successful maintenance of BNTU accounts in social media. At the same time, it was taken into account that the accounts were maintained either by an individual SMM specialist, or by a working group of employees from various departments of the library.

Comparative characteristics of indicators during the analysis of data on maintaining corporate social media personally and in a group was aimed at classifying them according to the following positions:

- Working time and frequency of headings preparation;
- Generation of ideas;
- Involvement;
- Burnout;
- Continuity;
- Competition;
- Upgrading.

Results

Consideration and analysis of the librarians' activities (SMM specialists and the working group) in corporate social media made it possible to summarize the advantages and risks of work, to characterize the main stages in its organization of group work.

Team building

The group consisted mainly of young employees who actively maintained their profiles and were well versed in the trends of a particular network. Young specialists of the library successfully establish contact with university students, take into account the trends when choosing content and a way of communication. The core of the group was made up of 10 people. Participation in the group is voluntary.

Communication and work organization

A platform for discussing the effectiveness of posts and the results of advertising campaigns is the Roundtable on Social Media, which takes place every month during the academic year. This is a basic activity that provides a guideline for the next month. The following questions are brought up for discussion:

- content plan, which is adjusted on the site;
- a calendar of memorable dates to prepare the material;
- proposals to use new approaches, analysis of interesting cases and posts;
- experience exchange in various programs and applications (for example, drawing up infographics, video processing).

In addition to the formal part of the discussion, it is important to maintain personal contact and communicate. Really bright creative ideas were born during face-to-face meetings and discussions. We use the Telegram group as a messenger.

Creativity and creative power

At the stage of group formation and assignment of headings to the participants, everyone could offer their own idea and present the first trial posts. It was very important to give the opportunity to express oneself. Many took advantage of this opportunity, and we received the first author's headings – #ancient game, #bureau of inventions, #something familiar, etc. (#древняядичь, #бюроизобретений, #чтотознакомое). Among the group members there were those who take great photographs, possess the skills of working in various photo and video editors. Our task is to expand the professional capabilities of employees, involve them in work, diversify their functionality and teach new practices. As a result we have a mix that more accurately reflects us as a library and collective.

Our experience of working in a group throughout the year and analysis of the results of promotion allow us to make a positive conclusion about the effectiveness of this approach in terms of management and content management. In the comparative table, according to most indicators, personal management of corporate accounts is inferior to work in a group (in the table, indicators are highlighted in gray).

Table 1

Maintaining corporate social media personally and in a group

Indicator	Personal maintenance of corporate accounts	Work in group
Management		
Work organization	<u>Individually</u> , personal content preparation plan, content plan	Periodic meetings with the group, content plan, presence of a manager, deadline control
Working time and frequency of headings preparation	Full time, meeting deadline	<u>Combining responsibilities and the risk of disrupting deadlines</u>
Generation of ideas	<u>Individually</u>	Active discussion, creative space, brainstorming
Involvement	<u>Individually</u> , independent search for inspiration	A platform for self-expression
Burnout	<u>Individually</u>	Collective support, the ability to pause and reformat content

Continuity	<u>Difficult</u>	Involvement/exit of participants on the current basis
Competition	External, third party organizations	External and internal; incentive to develop within the team
Upgrading	<u>Individually</u>	Peer learning, experience transfer
Feed formation		
Variety of content, number of headings (representation)	<u>Individually</u> , depends on the qualifications of the specialist	Variety of formats – photo, video content; the amount of content is maximum and is limited by the number of participants; specialization of participants, division of labor
Style and design of publications	<u>Individually</u> , uniform style	Unified style, discussion of options and approaches
Author's approach	<u>Individually</u>	Various author's headings
Competitor analysis	<u>Assigned to one person</u>	All participants collect interesting ideas and analyze competitors

Overcoming the challenges of group work

It is important to maintain interest in group work, develop creativity and stimulate initiative. Effective teamwork is based on management, the desire to inspire and support participants by one's own example. The main employment in departments is not in favor of participating in a group on social media, therefore, it is necessary to correctly calculate your strength and establish an objective frequency of headings preparation.

Content formation techniques

1. Video content

To attract attention, posts and stories are often accompanied by video content and animation, which has a positive effect on the views and coverage statistics. For the author's heading of personal conversations about the profession #you're not like a librarian (#тынепохожанабиблиотекаря) the video format was chosen. Preparing a video is a rather laborious and lengthy process, and this is justified. It is important to attract attention, to stop the subscriber's gaze while watching the feed.

2. Design trends

Our users include the students – the most creative, dynamic and demanding audience. We need to correspond and follow the trends, look modern and understandable. It is important to note that the content is primary, the material quality cannot be compensated for by visual effects alone.

3. Events, participation in projects

The work of creative team is not limited to social media. The group discusses issues of advertising support for the Scientific Library clubs – Cinema Club BNTU and Board Games Club “451,” bookcrossing, environmental projects and our participation in them.

4. Interaction with the university and its departments

Content sharing is an important source of promotion. Based on agreements, we have access to subscribers to the accounts of BNTU, the Youth Union and other departments. Such interaction is effective and we use various opportunities to convey information.

5. Mentions

Publications with mentions of persons, faculties, to which the material is related, become more visible and popular. Many of the accounts mentioned share our posts and influence coverage.

Potential

The work in the group allowed restructuring the work in social media throughout the year, to introduce new ideas and author's headings. The potential of this practice has not been exhausted and requires more detailed study and analysis.

Conclusions

As the results of our research show, according to most indicators, personal maintaining of corporate accounts is inferior to work in a group.

The experience of managing the process of forming a content policy when working in a group becomes more flexible and independent of the personality of an SMM specialist.

Working in a group allows producing creative and interesting content in large volumes, everything that can visually interest the user.

We choose different approaches to achieve “the main task of a modern librarian – to be a guide in the information and literary space” (Sorokina, 2021). Successful presentation on social media has a positive effect on the library's image, forms loyalty and ultimately leads to us in the library space.

REFERENCES

- Minasyan, A. Yu. (2019). «Instagram» i bibliotechnyy blog kak elementy populyarizatsii biblioteki i professii bibliotechnogo spetsialista v seti «internet». *Chelovek. Obshchestvo. Kultura. Sotsializatsiya. Materialy XV Mezhdunarodnoy molodezhnoy nauchno-prakticheskoy konferentsii, Ufa*, Ch. 1, 97-101. Retrieved from <https://bspu.ru/files/49477> (in Russian)
- Nechushkina, A. S. (2020). «Instagram» kak ploshchadka prodvizheniya moskovskikh bibliotek. *Sotsialno-gumanitarnye znaniya kak faktor izmeneniy sovremennogo obshchestva. Materialy mezhvuzovskoy studencheskoy nauchno-prakticheskoy konferentsii, Moscow*, 322-328. Retrieved from <https://www.elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=43099785> (in Russian)
- Sorokina, Ye. A. (2021). Sotsialnye seti kak instrument prodvizheniya bibliotek (na primere Instagram). *Denisevskie chteniya : Izbrannye materialy Shestnadsyatk i Semnadsyatk Denisevskikh chteniy: mezhunarodnoy nauchno-prakticheskoy konferentsii po bibliotekovedeniyu, bibliografovedeniyu, knigovedeniyu i problemam bibliotechno-informatsionnoy deyatelnosti 24 oktyabrya 2019 goda – 30 oktyabrya 2020 goda, Orel*, 215-218. Retrieved from <https://elibrary.ru/item.asp?id=44778651> (in Russian)

Yap, J. M. (2020). Library promotion and user engagement in pandemic times: the case of Kazakhstan. *University library at a new stage of social communications development. Conference proceedings*, 5, 39-46. doi: https://doi.org/10.15802/unilib/2020_220692 (in English)

SOBOLEVSKAYA Yu. V.

Наукова бібліотека Білоруського національного технічного університету (Республіка Білорусь, Мінськ), e-mail: sobol.yuli@gmail.com

РОБОТА У ГРУПІ АБО ПЕРСОНАЛЬНЕ ВЕДЕННЯ КОРПОРАТИВНИХ СОЦІАЛЬНИХ МЕРЕЖ

Мета. Соціальні мережі стали однією з основних технологій просування бібліотеки ВНЗ. Мета роботи – охарактеризувати основні етапи в організації роботи у соціальних мережах бібліотекарів (SMM-фахівців та робочої групи) Наукової бібліотеки Білоруського національного технічного університету (БНТУ). **Методика.** Інструменти статистичного аналізу дали змогу детально вивчити корпоративні мережі бібліотеки БНТУ. Проведено порівняльний аналіз досвіду ведення акаунтів БНТУ у соціальних мережах SMM-фахівцем та робочою групою співробітників з різних підрозділів бібліотеки. **Результати.** Узагальнено переваги та ризики у роботі групи. Виділено напрями: Формування команди; Комунікації та організація роботи; Креатив та творчий потенціал; Подолання викликів групової роботи; Прийоми формування контенту; Потенціал. **Висновки.** Робота у групі дозволяє виробляти креативний та цікавий контент у великих обсягах. Досвід управління процесом формування контент-політики у 2020 р. доводить, що процес став більш гнучким та незалежним від особи SMM-фахівця.

Ключові слова: соціальні мережі; корпоративні мережі університетської бібліотеки; SMM-фахівець та робочі групи

Received: 16.07.2021

Accepted: 29.11.2021